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Developing an Improved UMS (United Mining Supply) E-Payment System to Boost Customer Satisfaction

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ABSTRACT

The ICT and digital innovation era has caused dynamic corporate environment changes, with cash to electronic transactions shifting. The e-payment system was developed to complement, not replace, currency and trade barter. The reality that man cannot meet his wants has compelled trade. Trading has evolved from a rudimentary form to a sophisticated one. Bartering is a primordial type of trading. Barter trade is an essential answer to the problem of exchange, but it has several flaws. Man's inability to meet his own needs has compelled commerce. Trading has evolved from a rudimentary form to a sophisticated one. Electronic payments can be defined as a payment technique that uses electronic media and does not require currency. E-payment is a key part of e-commerce. We will analyze the literature on e-payment systems in e-commerce to emphasize the scope of the e-payment system and prior research methodologies to identify research gaps and suggest future studies. With the advent of the internet, electronic payments and transactions have exploded. Consumers could buy goods and services online and transfer unencrypted credit card details, compromising security and privacy. As consumers became more mindful of their privacy and security, new secure network payment solutions emerged. Unquantifiable benefits of e-payment include a cashless society and removing the fear of the unknown. With the effective utilization of e-payment technology, corruption in the government arena will be comprehensively tackled.

Keywords

e-banking, infrastructure, electronic payment, e-commerce, online.

1.0 Introduction

1.1 Research Background

After the scientific revolution, which had a tremendous impact on many elements of society, information and communication technology has facilitated the process of global corporate integration and the integration of independent firms functioning within a supply chain (1). Guinea is a country in West Africa with a population of 13 million people, according to information available on the Ministry of Communication and Information's website. Guinea is a country with a plethora of natural resources. A client has acquired a very important asset for sustainable development companies; therefore, clear planning and strategies are necessary for businesses to retain customers and be satisfied. For the consumer, the grouping known as the improvement payment process is useful for businesses because improving the customer's payment process is one of the appropriate characteristics for customer satisfaction(2). Therefore, this article proposes to find new strategies to improve the UMS payment platform by adding local payments for customer satisfaction. Make the platform easy to use by improving some icons. Secure the customer's payment and put a simple method to facilitate the flow of responsiveness to meet customer satisfaction according to the needs of the business. The importance of this research is the improvement of the payment method. The purchasing payment process can add visibility, allowing management to communicate better with suppliers on where the items are located; the delivery process and suppliers' payment boost customer service and cash flow. The problem of mutual desire overlap, among other things, is a key impediment to the system's development. Guinea is leading the e-payment system, growing increasingly popular because of its convenience, as part of an emerging generation of information technology (IT) surveys. Offline digital cash (for example, ATM, Master Card, and Visa International) is on the rise, with cards (metal or plastic) being used for withdrawals on dedicated machines designed for the purpose. The online UMS E-payment system, which uses PCs with internet connections, is becoming more popular.

1.2 Purpose of Study

The frequency with which financial transactions are completed has increased dramatically. The widespread usage of paper cash progressively gives way to a new payment system, namely, the electronic payment transaction system (also known as the E-payment system). According to a survey of the country's developing generation of information technology professionals, Guineans are pushing the e-payment system, which is becoming increasingly popular due to its convenience, to the forefront of their minds. But the growing popularity of offline E-payment (for example, ATMs and credit cards from companies such as MasterCard and Visa International) results from the use of cards (metal or plastic) for withdrawals from special devices that have been created particularly for this purpose. However, computers and telephone lines for online transactions are on the rise. However, the absence of proper security has been a key hurdle in the growth of the e-payment transaction system, owing to the country's increasing tendency of corruption. Given the current global trend, it is reasonable to conclude that the performance of Guinea's electronic payment system will be a major predictor of economic growth. The research is especially important in the Guinean

economy, where a lack of proper security has hampered the continuous rise of electronic payments. It aims to investigate potential software design features for safeguarding the E-payment system against fraudulent transactions.

2.0 System Review (Literature Review and

2.1 Overview

A strong supply chain is critical to a company's ability to adapt quickly to new opportunities and capitalize on growth opportunities. As a result, its impact on customer satisfaction can be seen in various areas, including communication, purchasing strategy, technical optimization, and, in particular, the payment process. Maryam Bayat and Mehdi Shajari both worked on a similar topic. They emphasized the role of the contextual payment system; WANG Yan 'WANG Yan-yan also worked on the purchasing system flow and payment for ERP Enterprises. In this section, the research described the respondent and the literature review that addresses the improvement aspect of the payment system. In my case of study, it is very hard for the countries where the technology is not well developed. For example, UMS is a company based in Guinea. It is also a large company with an international price; due to the lack of some elements, it is very difficult to energize the company in terms of SCM on the local side. These basics should be used in other business areas to satisfy customers. Through my research, I will discuss how UMS can be more efficient in the payment process to meet customers' satisfaction in the region. Most retail customers are not educated, so it is very difficult for them to make the payment because those who pay by local transaction most of the time need people who have visa cards and main cards. I want to say the transaction account required to buy stuff. Not only are the customers interested in this situation, but the local vendor who also adds or improves the payment process in the area will help the business keep their customers and their vendor until customer satisfaction. The potential problem caused by using an international rather than a local account is delaying payment to customers due to the lack of a payment method in their app, which can also affect their relationships with local providers, not forgetting how to secure the customer. Whole processes, after adding local payment and making the platform or application easy for the customers to use, help the business to avoid payment fraud.

2.2 What is an E-Payment Solution?

An e-payment solution is a credit card or mobile money terminal that allows your members or customers to make contributions or transactions. Members would have to pay using mobile money - which is more convenient since the payment process is faster and it takes less time for the money to reach your SSNIT account. Online payments and contributions are, by far, the most convenient and time-efficient mode of payment for both you and your clients. In modern banking services, the use of technology generally referred to as electronic payment systems increase banking performance by allowing a wide range of operations to be completed quickly and correctly without compromising production (3). Electronic payments are payment mechanisms that use electronic media that do not involve cash (4). Electronic payment systems are also inter-organizational information linked to transaction systems, associations, and clients. Partners, technology

and the environment must interact complexly. Payment information for goods and services is retrieved and placed in an electronic template that creates electronic files for network processing, according to the Federal Financial Institutions Examination Council (2010). Electronic payments are the electronic value transfer of a payment from the payer to the recipient. The e-payment service has a web-based user interface that allows consumers to remotely access and manage their bank accounts (4). The term e-payment refers to electronic payment in online transactions conducted over the Internet, defined as any transaction including electronic funds. Electronic payments are also referred to as a paperless payment method in some circles (5).

2.2.1 Types of Electronic Payment

Customers use prepaid cards for a certain amount by entering unique card numbers on merchant sites, and credit cards are servers that authenticate consumers and verify the bank whether sufficient funds are available before purchasing, debit cards are the customer maintains a positive balance in the bank account and the money deducted by the Acco (4). It comprises online credit card transactions, e-wallets, e-cash, value systems that are saved on the internet, digitally collected balance systems, wireless payment systems, and digital check payment systems, among other things (5). Electronic payment instruments commonly used in the retail business are credit cards, card fees, debit cards, and e-money (5). The structure of this online digital cash transaction system is very similar to the one used in the existing paper cash system. In the online digital cash transaction system, three main components are the bank, the customer, and the merchants. The user can withdraw or shop directly online from the merchant, and the money is deducted from his/her account. The user in (pin code) in this online digital cash transaction is fully anonymous, and it is done by using a protocol. It is good to hide the user's ID (pin codes), but this raises the problem of lacking since the digital cash transaction represents a user's wallet.

2.3.2. The Evolution of the Electronic Payment System

In the offline scheme, withdrawal and shopping are very online schemes. The main difference is in the transaction part model. Instead of verifying cash during every transaction, the security is guaranteed without the direct involvement of the bank. It is achieved by adding a temper resistance device at the point of sale known as a smart card reader. The device is trusted by the bank and is used to verify the card's authenticity. This device makes the whole transaction offline.

The payment system has evolved dramatically with technology. In 1914, a shopping center, Oil Company, and Western Union produced a customer card to make paying for goods or services easier for customers. Initially, all credit card payments were made on paper until the 1990s, when the card was completely turned into an electronic device (4). The Federal Reserve Bank made the first telegraph transfer of currency in 1918, marking the beginning of the growth of electronic payments (5). Despite their designation in 1960, electronic cashless payments are widely used today due to e-commerce and technological advancements. The research community has worked tirelessly to build online payment methods like Asokan N. and JW (4).

2.3 Theoretical Framework of the Study

2.3.1 *Process payment system*

Digital payment systems have developed and grown rapidly and complexly since the 1960s. The Electronic Fund Transfer (EFT) was created following the traditional payment system development. It was the first system of electronic payments to rely on a central processor. The Electronic Data Interchange (EDI) financial application for electronic transferral of funds sends a card or electronic checks through secure private networks to banks and key companies.

2.3.2 *Payment systems in Guinea*

While the Central Bank of Guinea (CBL) has not yet adopted DPS in Guinea, it has sought to establish a national system of payments based on various banks' network development initiatives. In terms of bank services in Guinea, it has taken pioneering steps. Payment systems have been expanding in Guinea in the last couple of years. Systems are based on advanced applications accessed throughout the Internet that allow the country to develop electronic means of payment that contribute to its banking and financial services sector's diversity, speed, and accuracy. New investment horizons have also opened up. The Central Bank of Guinea has taken these factors to take steps to develop a banking sector that can keep pace with international development. The Guinean Central Bank has initiated a scheduling process, launched a national payment system, and prepared for technical studies and strategic planning. Through contracts with international companies specializing in implementing the project components of the national payment system, the Central Bank of Guinea has implemented these steps.

2.3.4 *Online customer satisfaction*

Electronic commerce companies proffer a range of Web-based resources to improve services to the customer, including personalized apps, chat rooms, e-mail, automated responding, support desks, and call centers. Product or service satisfaction rating based on consumer feedback. Corporate and individual clients may buy a product or service for quite different reasons, therefore, any assessment of perception must account for this. Quality post-sale services can also influence purchasing decisions. Consumers in e-commerce and traditional consumer business models differ greatly. The Internet is becoming more complex as web technology leads to a more difficult index of consumer satisfaction assessment. Previous information systems researchers are mainly researchers, and the impact on customer satisfaction is more focused on an e-commerce system. As can be seen, confidence has an effect and is affected by various factors, and a key factor in MPS adoption is the relationship between these variables. In this sense, understanding consumer requirements for building confidence is crucial for businesses to enhance their satisfaction and services for users insofar as customer relations are more difficult to maintain because of fewer face-to-face contacts (Bourreau and Valetti, 2015). Therefore, providers need to create 'initial confidence' for users (Zhou, 2014). In this regard, payment sector entities, particularly the MPS market, should provide customers with the full functionality of the measures to protect customer information. Xin (2013) indicated that 'consumers build their confidence through the mobile service providers' credibility and the perceived environmental risk,

systemic assurance, and mobile payment providers.' Zhou (2013) defines the key factor affecting trust as 'service efficiency.' Shaw (2014) also shows concerns about privacy and security, which have a major impact on trust. However, Teoh et al. (2013) disputed this and revealed that the trust and security perception of the consumer regarding e-payment is insignificant. Some scholars indicated that consumers need to learn about mobile payment systems or know how they work. Slade et al. (2015) found that 'including MP information as a moderation variable showed that the impact on the behavior of those who understood MP was significantly different from those who knew MP.

2.3.4 Effect of digital payments on customer satisfaction via e-commerce

The daily increase in the internet and e-commerce has changed the way products and services are marketed and sold. The development of electronic information resources and the development of the digital age have resulted in numerous new problems for product sellers and information services providers. The Internet changes the way companies deal with their consumers, who expect ever-higher services, are saved time and want more convenience. Given how we manage service quality – which matters greatly to customer satisfaction – is one of the principal tasks of the internet as a communication channel, this research aims to better understand the impact of website quality factors on customer satisfaction. Moreover, customer satisfaction and mobile, as well as internet banking, have the strongest influence. Customer satisfaction is affected by POS systems the least. A recent study has also been carried out by Ogochukwu et al. (2018), which analyzed customer satisfaction with electronic insurance procurement payments in Nigeria. Simple random technology and questionnaire took part in the metropolitan of Lagos, with 278 respondents. The result was a lack of customer satisfaction regarding electronic payment systems in insurance product procurement. Their research suggests that insurance undertakings should improve the informing of the insurance public on the various payment methods of electronic insurance acquisitions to ensure greater involvement through the electronic process. That government itself should create a public atmosphere to avoid continuous net failure. It trains insurers in the dynamics of electronic payment systems.

2.3.5 Digital payment systems definition

The Digital Payment Services (DPS) standard describes the key entities involved and transaction processes since the emergence of e-commerce. Significant work is being done. Business via the Internet and the subsequent development of DPS has given rise to a dynamic environment in which the major benefits of business transactions for online strategies are without the remedy of face-to-face interaction (Raza and Hanif, 2013). Several studies have described digital payment in numerous ways. Tennyson and Mercy (2014), in the case of electronic signals between financial institutions, have described digital payment as a kind of monetary transaction in which funding is transferred instead of exchanging checks, cash, or other negotiable instruments.

In addition, there are several advantages in enhancing financial reporting efficiency by using electronic payment systems, to reduce corruption, to pre-condition electronic payments, including protection, universality, cost-effective, speed, accessibility, acceptability, convenience, and privacy (Nwanking and Ajemunigbohun, 2016; Tennyson and Mercy, 2014). As a result, DPS activities are becoming increasingly popular, with several payment methods being developed to facilitate online money exchange. Debit and credit cards aren't the only payment options available in the DPS system. Users can utilize EPS for P2P and DPS (Anyanwu et al., 2012). Khalili et al. (2012) argue that both trade and electronic systems are developed by EPS, which helps users avoid using credit cards. With the initial broad adoption of the Internet, the potential for commercial use and, in particular, e-commerce was highly anticipated. Because these forecasts were short-term too optimistic, trade and political focus turned to obstacles in the development of e-commerce. OECD household surveys have highlighted several trade barriers, such as consumer resistance to payment online (Abili and Jafarnejad, 2014).

Several problems related to online payment systems were often used as one of several important factors to explain the slow growth of electronic trade. Such claims partly addressed the abuse of online shopping due to an absence of appropriate payment systems, consumer confidence in electronic payments, and/or the issues with perceived payment security mechanisms. In other words, payment problems and other variables such as product inadequacy, unknown sellers and buyers, and uncertain distribution conditions were seen as significant reasons. A payment system's main function is to provide a means to transfer value among various economic parties. As such, the cost of the transaction is partly economic. It will allow fast and efficient transfers of value while requiring minimum extra costs and risks. According to Jayaram and Prasad (2013), the number of online financial services apps grows rapidly. The importance of the Internet in DPS, which serves as a platform for online transactions such as online shopping, online auctions, stock trading, and other similar activities, is underlined. However, although EPS offers many advantages, including increased speed transactions and lower management charges, uncertainty and security concerns remain. EPS has been recognized as a key tool for supporting online transactions (Teoh et al., 2013), so the nature of payment may be defined.

2.4 Information and Electronic Payment Systems

Using the theoretical basis of information and computation to explore diverse business models and related algorithmic processes inside a computer science discipline, the study connects business and computer science. An information system, according to Singh (2004), is comprised of information technology and human activities that support operations, management, and decision-making. An information system, on the other hand, is a combination of people, procedures, data, and technology (Singh,2004). In this context, the phrase refers to an organization's use of information and communication technology (ICT) and how people interact with it to support business activities. An information system is a collection of components that work together to gather, store, and process data, as well as distribute information, knowledge, and digital goods.

Information systems are used by businesses and other organizations to carry out and manage operations, engage with consumers and suppliers, and compete in the marketplace (James, 2009).

Shon and Swatman (1998) coined the term electronic payment system to describe any electronic financial transfer. Kalakota and Whinston (1997) defined an electronic e-commerce payment as an online financial exchange. According to Abrazhevich (2004), electronic payment systems enable the most crucial action after the customer decides to pay. Several successful electronic payment systems have been developed (Kalakota and Winston, 1996), including smart cards, electronic currency, and electronic cheque mechanisms. (Harris et al., 2011) For example, Singh (2009) categorizes electronic payment systems into four types: online credit card payment, online electronic cash, electronic check, and smart card-based electronic payment. To pay securely online fees, the researchers focused on debit and credit cards. According to Mohammad and Emmanuel (2003), a credit card processing cycle involves six parties: consumer, card issuer, merchant bank, acquirer, and credit card processor. To receive payments, the merchant creates a bank account with the card issuing bank. To accept credit cards, a business must first register with an acquirer, a bank or other financial institution that sets up an account and provides a credit card terminal. Credit card network maintains a huge data center that operates as a clearinghouse for all credit card transactions (Mohammad and Emmanuel, 2003).

2.5 Role of Electronic Payments in Customer E-Commerce Activities

Customers' online purchasing activities include payment. The Consumer Mercantile Activities Model accurately describes these activities (Kalakota & Whinston, 1997). The model is divided into three phases: pre-purchase interaction, purchase consummation, and post-purchase interaction. "The purchase consummation phase specifies the flow of information and documents connected with purchasing and negotiating relevant terms, such as price, availability, and delivery dates, with merchants; and electronic payment technologies that incorporate payment into the purchasing process" (Kalakota & Whinston, 1997). Following the identification of the products or services to be acquired, the buyer proceeds to payment activities. A commercial transaction is carried out by the buyer and seller. In a mercantile transaction, the buyer and seller exchange information before making the required payment. Payment methods should be mutually agreed upon and arranged (ibid). As a result, in order to complete a successful e-commerce commercial transaction, the buyer must be willing to use the payment option given by merchants. The user's approval of e-commerce EPSs is critical for the buy completion phase and the full purchasing process. Thus, payment processing and user interaction are crucial for e-commerce. According to Delali (2010) in Fiallos & Wu (2005), the introduction of the internet accelerated the rise of electronic payments and transactions. Consumers could buy things via the internet and send unencrypted credit card numbers across the network, which provided little protection and privacy. However, as consumers become more concerned about their privacy and security, a plethora of new secure network payment systems have emerged. Financial

institutions, banks, and retailers all gain greatly from digital money (Fiallos & Wu, 2005). Digital Money is an electronic payment technique that, like paper cash, may allow anonymous flexible electronic payment, but with the added security standards required for online transactions. According to Lee, Choi, and Rhee (2003), a secure electronic cash system can ensure the privacy of legitimate users while also providing traceability of illegally issued cash or laundered money. If unlawful conduct occurs, the anonymity of digital cash can be revoked in order to safeguard the bank. According to Lee, Oh, and Lee (2004), digital money is a surefire technique of guarding against illicit redistribution of intellectual property and materials since it can trace double-spending and double-spending safeguards content by exposing the double-identity. spender's Digital money can also be used to discourage unlawful content copying and distribution by including content considerations into the digital cash payment structure, preventing users from engaging in individual replication activity (Lee, Oh & Lee, 2004). Using this capability, legal, anonymous purchasers can distribute content to other paying, anonymous users while adhering to copyright regulations. Using digital money in industries such as digital entertainment might raise demand for products by making distribution easier and safer. Digital money can track down who is illegally replicating and distributing copyrighted intellectual property, boosting author security while delaying lost revenue and sales for digital media entertainment firms (Lee, Oh & Lee, 2004).

Digital Media Entertainment and property suppliers and distributors can also use this technology and its safety features to ensure more copyright compliance among users (Fiallos & Wu, 2005). Software and intellectual property piracy can be reduced and eventually abolished by using such a payment and distribution approach. Digital money can provide financial organizations with decentralized structures, faster transaction and decision-making processes, and more cost-effective business strategies. Apart from ease and security, electronic payments, as claimed by (Taddesse & Kidan 2005), provide a substantial number of economic benefits. When these advantages are leveraged, they can make a significant contribution to a country's economic progress. Automated electronic payments help to deepen bank deposits, boosting funds available for commercial loans, which are a driver of total economic activity. Electronic payments that are efficient, safe, and convenient have various macroeconomic benefits, according to Taddesse and Kidan (2005). "The impact of adopting electronic payments is analogous to riding a bicycle with gears." Add an efficient electronic payment system to an economy, and it will accelerate. Add better-controlled consumer and business lending, and economic velocity rises even more" (Taddesse & Kidan 2005).

Cardholders help to keep money in the banking system by using their cards at the point of sale. EPS can aid in the displacement of shadow economies, the integration of concealed transactions into the banking system, and the enhancement of transparency, confidence, and participation in the financial system. Taddesse and Kidan (2005) discovered a link between rising point-of-sale volumes and rising demand deposits. "Automated electronic payments serve as an entry point into the banking sector as well as a potent growth engine." Such payments move cash out of circulation and into bank accounts, providing low-cost capital to

support bank lending for investment—a driver of total economic activity. The method increases transparency and accountability, resulting in increased efficiency and improved economic performance.

Electronic payment is quite convenient for the consumer. You will most likely only need to enter your account information once, such as your payment card number and mailing address, in order to complete your transaction. Following that, the information is saved in a database on the retailer's web server. When you return to the website, all you have to do is enter your username and password. A transaction can be completed with a single click of the mouse: all that is left is to confirm your purchase and you are done. Worku (2010) underlined that electronic payment saves firms money. The more electronic payments that are processed, the less money is spent on paper and mail. Offering electronic payment can also assist firms in increasing client retention. "A customer is more likely to return to an e-commerce site where he or she has already input and kept information."

"Electronic payments, according to Taddesse and Kidan (2005), cut transaction costs, generate higher consumption and GDP, improve government efficiency, increase financial intermediation, and improve financial transparency." According to the authors, governments have a vital role in fostering a climate in which these benefits can be realized in a way that is consistent with their own economic growth objectives.

When electronic payment instruments are developed and widely used, they have the potential to benefit businesses and customers alike by making payment and settlement for a potentially enormous range of products and services offered globally via the internet or other electronic networks easier, more convenient, and more secure. Electronic payments enable consumers to conduct their daily financial transactions without the need to physically visit a bank branch or financial institution. Electronic payments have the potential to save merchants both time and money (Appiah & Agyemang, 2007).

A country's payment system may cost 13 percent of GDP in resources. The societal cost of a payment system may be greatly reduced if electronic payments are made instead of paper-based non-cash payments (Appiah & Agyemang, 2007). Automating and streamlining electronic payments through self-serve channels like ATMs, branch office terminals, and POS systems can cut paper-based errors and expenses significantly. Consumers, retailers, banks, and the economy benefit from electronic payments, according to Visa Canada Association and Global Insight research. Since 1983, electronic payments have added \$107 billion to the Canadian economy, approximately 25% of the \$437 billion cumulative growth (Delali, 2010). Credit cards (C49.4 billion) outperformed debt cards (C10.4 billion) in terms of growth in personal consumer expenditures during the same two decades (Delali, 2010). Nigeria lags far behind much of the globe in minimizing the importance of physical currency in daily transactions and fostering the emergence of a cashless society; this may be avoided (Dankwambo, 2009). However, financial experts warn that unless something radical new is introduced that caters for attitudes and the large unbanked population, the country's aim of a cashless society in the shortest time feasible may be unattainable (Dankwambo, 2009).

2.5.1 Business-to-consumer Payment Systems

The goal of this study is to determine whether or not new payment systems are accepted by consumers in e-commerce contexts. A country's payment system may consume 13% of its GDP. Paper-based non-cash payments can significantly minimize the social cost of a payment system (Appiah & Agyemang, 2007).

2.5.2 Payment Systems designed for the Web

Consumer e-commerce is now mostly done over the Internet's WWW (Web) service. The market for e-commerce payments via wireless PDAs, mobile phones, and other Internet services is still developing (Bohle, 2001a), hence user base and usage experience are limited. Web-based e-commerce EPSs and Web-based e-commerce apps are covered.

2.6 Electronic Payment System in Guinea and its Benefits

According to Delali (2010) in Fiallos, the introduction of the internet accelerated the rise of electronic payments and transactions. Consumers could buy things via the internet and send unencrypted credit card numbers across the network, which provided little protection and privacy. However, as consumers become more concerned about their privacy and security, a plethora of new secure network payment systems have emerged. The method increases transparency and accountability, resulting in increased efficiency and improved economic performance. For the consumer, electronic payment is quite handy. Most of the time, you only need to input your account information once, such as your payment card number and mailing address. After that, the data is saved in a database on the retailer's web server. When you return to the website, you simply enter your username and password. "Completing a transaction is as easy as clicking your mouse: all you have to do is confirm your purchase and you're done." Worku (2010) stressed the notion that electronic payment saves firms money. The more electronic payments that are processed, the less money is spent on paper and mail. Offering electronic payment can also assist firms in increasing client retention. "A customer is more likely to return to an e-commerce site where he or she has already input and kept information."

One such advantage is that electronic payments allow bank customers to conduct everyday financial activities without having to visit a local bank location. Electronic payment products could save retailers time and money when dealing with cash (Appiah & Agyemang, 2007). Paper-based errors and expenses can be reduced by automating and streamlining electronic payments made through self-service channels like as ATMs, branch office terminals, and point-of-sale (POS) systems. Electronic payments deliver transactional efficiency to customers, businesses, banks, and the economy, according to research conducted by Visa Canada Association in conjunction with Global Insight. Since 1983, electronic payments have contributed \$107 billion to the Canadian economy, accounting for roughly a quarter of the Canadian economy's total increase of \$437 billion over the same period (Delali, 2010). Over the same two decades, electronic payments accounted for \$C60 billion of the increase in personal consumption expenditures, with credit cards

accounting for a lion's share of this growth (\$C49.4 billion) against debt cards (\$C10.4 billion) (Delali, 2010). Guinea lags far behind the rest of the world in the broad drive to enhance microeconomic activity by minimizing the importance of physical cash in daily transactions and supporting the development of a cashless society; however, this can be avoided (Dankwambo, 2009). Financial experts have warned, however, that unless something radically innovative, functional, and savvy is introduced that takes into account attitudes as well as the country's large unbanked population, the country's dream of building a functionally cashless society in the shortest time possible may be elusive (Dankwambo, 2009).

2.8 Challenges of Electronic Payments

Even in the developed world, electronic payments have inherent drawbacks, despite their tremendous advantages. As described by Ogedebe and Babatunde (2012) in Sumanjeet (2009), the challenges militating against e-payment mainly revolve around.

- Integrity*: to ascertain that transmitted financial information is unchanged in transit.

- Non-reputation*: to ascertain that all parties have non-deniable proof of receipt.

- Confidentiality*: to ascertain that transactions are protected from possible eavesdroppers.

- Reliability*: to ascertain that there is a reduced possibility of failure.

- Authorization*: to ensure that individuals are acknowledged and that the appropriate rights and privileges are conferred. The system, which is still in its early stages, requires a great deal of knowledge and education of the people in order for them to realize the commendable program put in place by a government to defend their interests. If they are properly and thoroughly informed, there is a good possibility that the program will be fully accepted. Banks must also be included in the implementation process because they play an important role.

3.0 Proposed System

3.1 Methodology

Research begins with identifying the problems. In this step, the problem is improving the payment process by adding local payments. Next, the literature review will examine the factor based on the principles of payment system law. In detail, the study creates the model as shown in the figures. The last step will describe the result. The descriptive-analytical approach tries to compare, explain and evaluate in the hope of reaching meaningful generalizations that can increase knowledge on this topic. The first one will be the analytical and practical method which is a tool that you can use to add the local payment on the platform or the system. This type of method will allow you to change the payment method to add a local transaction using visual elements, Building trust and security for customers to complete their transactions. Making the payment process easy to use helps the customer to save time by adapting the local payment methods to the customer's needs. Help the customer to remember the payment details before a future purchase simplify by especially improving the logo from the payment provider that you can increase when the transaction is declined, make the platform easy to use, be sure to include these parameters.

- 1- *Try another payment method.*
- 2- *Cancel the payment.*
- 3- *View all transactions.*
- 4- *Improve the UMS payment platform by adding local payments like Orange money Mobile Money.*

3.2 ISM Methodology and Model Development

Interpretative structural modeling is a qualitative research technique, and we all know one of the major purposes in supply chain management is to establish a relationship or build a relationship that can meet customer satisfaction. Interpretive Structural Modeling (ISM) is an interactive learning process in which a set of different and directly related elements are structured into the model of a complete system (6, 7). The model thus formed depicts the structure of a complex question or problem, of a system, or of a field of study. The ISM methodology helps to impose order and direction on the complex relationships between the customer and companies in the supply chain. Different steps are involved in ISM modeling. But I will deal with supply chain risk factors security factors on the payment process. ISM offers a variety of advantages, such as the process being systematic; the computer is programmed to consider all possible relationships by pairs of system elements, either directly from participants' responses or by transitive inference. If the process is effective, depending on the context, the use of transitive inference may reduce the number of relational queries required from 50 to 80 percent(6). For me, the starting point of this method is our mindset, and I mean a mental model, which means creating a relationship through our mind as we are looking for supply chain management performance.

3.3 Online Payment System Developments

In today's society, globalization is the outcome of new technical endeavors. The advancement of technology has altered the skyline of payment systems, bringing them closer to the eWorld (3). Clearly, modern innovation has transformed traditional payment systems into a more efficient and viable system that is free of the cash-and-carry dysfunction. The effectiveness of conducting financial transactions, as well as more secure and faster access to cash, among other factors, has propelled an e-payment system ahead of the paper money-based framework. (5)[(8)7]. Interestingly, in Guinea, the online payment framework is picking up eminence to the degree that clients have now wanted to do financial transactions without going to the banks. Thus, the time of money-based payment framework is slowly blurring out as the cashless economy dominates present-day financial systems (3, 9). Lately, the online payment system has turned into a standard through which fiscal element moves advantageously, particularly in a developing country like Guinea, where it is habitual to carry cash. In such a country, the online payment system has shaped into an important starting point of her present-day economy; a well-working system of online payment has been perceived to have much pertinence to budgetary strength, overall financial activity, and monetary policy (4). In the meantime, the initiative for an economy that is not based on cash will be preferred in the new era only when

it is supported with age advantage, good education, ownership of important innovative foundations, among different other components, appropriately set up by every concerned individual of the economic system and proficiently managed before forcing the citizens to comply. Several types of research were done on the systems of online payment and the development of the economy at the current time.

3.4 Payment System Regulation Factors

The payment system is a multi-party system that regulates the transfer of money from one account to another. The payment system is governed by four fundamental principles: security, fairness, efficiency, and consumer protection. All of these elements must also work with the non-cash payment system(9).

Figure 3.1 Payment System

All factors exhibit in table I are available in the regulation (Law) of the payment system in the UMS Company.

-Secure transactions and information make up the security aspect. This element indicates the transaction's security during payment execution as well as the customer's information in the system.

-The time is included in the efficiency factor. This component describes the time of using the payment process.

- The equity factor is a factor that indicates the fairness of information to the seller and buyer during payment without any special treatment towards each other or between seller and buyer in a transaction.

-The final aspect is consumer protection, which entails safeguarding all client information, such as customer data confidentiality and payment transaction information.

To ensure that the customer's privacy is safeguarded both during and after the payment transaction is completed.

Figure 3.2 Online Payment System Process

3.6 Summary Proposed System

The electronic payment system is the alternative to the coin or paper-based cash payment system to make it easy for the user to contribute to the groups they belong to our services over the network or internet and in the absence of the physical (entity) presence. Initially, cheques in bank payment systems are used to serve the purpose of the same, but now in the era of the internet and e-commerce, paying securely over the internet is an important task for the electronic payment system. Currently, credit cards are also in use for payments over the network, but still, user's doubt about trustworthiness and the security of their money because of the increase in frauds which ultimately causes loss of value (money) either of users, merchants, or participating banks. Present electronic payment systems are too far from ideal payment systems because of the higher transaction cost, more fraudulent activities, and multiple parties are involved in the payment processing simultaneously lacks user's acceptance, proper application plans, and incompatible standards/specifications. A good payment system should satisfy the user's acceptance and merchants on a mass scale. The present electronic payment system can be divided into two group's electronic cash and credit/debit system or token-based, and account-based system Tokens or electronic cash are like the physical cash which represent the value and credit/debit, or account-based system does not carry value but a message to transfer value.

4.0 System Design and Development

4.1 The Proposed System

The UMS E-payment system will provide an additional channel for online contributions to the UMS Fund and will integrate with existing systems. The UMS E-payment system was proposed to address issues associated with the current payment methods for fund contributions, which favor only government employees. The UMS E-payment system is a different platform that allows Non-formal Sector workers and their sponsors to safely contribute online using credit and debit cards or mobile money.

Figure 4.1: UMS E-payment System Flowchart

4.2 System Requirement

4.2.1 Functional Requirements

➤ *Customers*

These users typically do not have a high level of professional education and may not be computer proficient.

➤ *System administrator*

Most of the time, these users have a high degree of professional education, are computer savvy, and have had extensive training in the manufacturing process. These users are responsible for performing administrative duties and configuring the system.

➤ *Payment gateway provider*

The business that provides electronic payment services. For a fee, this company accepts electronic payment transactions.

➤ *Payment gateway device*

For payment transactions, the payment gateway provider's electronic device or server communicates with the point of sale. The Payment gateway device manages this payment transaction, which might be accepted or rejected. Refunds can also be managed by payment gateway devices.

The functional requirements define how the system should behave. This behavior could take the shape of services, tasks, or operations that the system must perform. It is useful in product development to differentiate between the baseline capabilities required for any system to compete in that product domain and features that distinguish the system from rival products and variants within your company's own product line/family. Additional functionality or functionality that differs from the essential functionality, as well as some quality trait, are examples of features (such as performance or memory utilization).

4.2.3 Non-Functional Requirements

- The system should be easy to maintain.
- The system should be compatible with different platforms.
- The system should be fast as customers always need speed.
- The system should always be available online at all times.
- The system should be secure.
- The system should be accessible to online users.
- The system should be easy to learn by both sophisticated and novice users.
- The system should provide easy, navigable, and user-friendly interfaces.
- The system should produce reports in different forms such as tables and graphs for easy visualization by management.
- The system should have a standard graphical user interface that allows for the online data entry, editing, and deleting of data with much ease

Figure 4.2 Functional Requirements

4.3 Design of Proposed System

There are several relevant concepts that should be considered in program design.

This is concerned with what tasks the computer can do how they do them, and here we stop briefly to face the fact that there are many problems that computers cannot solve, not just for a particular reason but because the task can be proven to be theoretically impossible. A task may be said to be computable if it can be in principle be performed by a machine. It is measured in terms of the quality of resources used. The main resource considerations are time and storage. Clearly, for many tasks, there may be an alternative solution, and for practical reasons, knowledge of their complexity will make the best choice. A program is correct when it meets its specification. In an ideal world, when we have completed the implementation of any program, we would be able to state with certainty that the program is accurate; it is important to demonstrate with certainty that the program will generate the desired result when all allowed inputs are provided to it. The system produces the complete detailed specification of the proposed system. It indicates how it will look and what it would offer its users. The major phase leading to the design of this new system includes:

- 1) Input Design
- 2) Output Design
- 3) Database Design
- 4) Control Design
- 5) Feature of the programming language used.

4.3 Benefits/Advantages of the proposed system

1. Time savings: Transferring money between virtual accounts normally takes a few minutes, whereas you will not lose time standing in lines at a bank or post office.
2. Expense control: Even if someone is eager to keep his disbursements under control, he must be patient enough to record all small expenses, which sometimes account for a significant portion of the overall amount of disbursements.

3. Lower danger of loss and theft: You can't leave your virtual wallet someplace and it can't be stolen by criminals.
 4. Reasonably priced commissions You will be charged a hefty cost if you pay for an internet service provider or a mobile account refill using a UPT (unattended payment terminal).
 5. Simple to use. Every service is often designed to reach the broadest potential audience, therefore it has an easily understandable user interface.
- Five. Convenience. All transactions can be completed at any time and from any location. It is sufficient to have Internet connectivity.

Figure 4.4: Matrix Formular Diagram

This format is transformed in the format of reachable matrix by transforming the information of each entry, so I'm going to explain to you how self-structure interaction matrix; this method has four symbols VAXO.

Now we use

V - for the relation from I to j but not in both directions;

A - for the relation from j to me but not in both directions;

X - for both direction relations from I to j and j to I;

O - The relation between the elements does not appear to be valid.

It is creating a reachability matrix based on the SSIM (self-structural interactive matrix) and testing for transitivity. is focused with the creation of the M reachability matrix. It is a binary matrix because the SSIM entries V, A, X, and O are translated to 1 and 0 according to the following rules: Risks in the supply chain, according to ISM.

- If the I J) item in the SSIM is V, the I J) entry in the reachability matrix is one, and the (j, I entry is 0.
- If the SSIM I j) entry is A, the reachability matrix I j) entry becomes 0 and the (j, I entry becomes 1.
- If the I J) entry in the SSIM is X, then the reachability matrix's I J) and (j, I entries both become 1.
- If the SSIM's I j) entry is O, then the reachability matrix's I j) and (j, I entries are both 0.

Figure 4.4: Customer Data flow Diagram

4.4 Data-Flow Diagram

Software analysts and designers employ a range of diagrams, not for the purpose of diversity, but to highlight different features of a system. Data-flow diagrams, for example, indicate the system's functionalities, state-transition diagrams show the system's timings, and entity-relationship diagrams display the data relationships. Software developers' diagrams are also influenced by their development culture, which includes what most people are familiar with, your spec-writing guidelines and whether the software organization primarily produces transactional systems or object-oriented systems, and so forth. Here are showed some of the most popular software diagrams, along with a few versions of each. See Resources for further information on different forms of software diagrams. The data-flow diagram (also known as a DFD, bubble chart, process model, business-flow model, workflow diagram, or function model) is useful for demonstrating system functions but is ineffective for modeling databases or time-dependent behavior (Figure 4-5).

Processes or functions are depicted as circles or, in some cases, rounded rectangles. A process is a representation of a system component that performs input-to-output conversion. As an example, the label "Find DFD information" might be a good choice for the process' label.

Flows are depicted as arrowed lines (either straight or curved). The label should indicate what type of information or object is moving along the flow, for as "Weblink."

Two parallel lines or an open-ended rectangle depict a store (a location where data is stored). A store isn't available in every system. "Web links" is a common example of a label that is often the plural form of the item's name, such as "Web links." Labels are typically brought in and out of the store by the flow. (The flows into and out of the store will have the same labels because the same products are brought in and out.) Rectangles represent terminators, external entities, or persons with whom the system communicates.

5.1 Implementation of System

The system implementation and documentation is the phase of system development that constitutes proof of the making of the new system. Planning the implementation of a system begins in the detailed design stage. This phase of the project will involve the installation and testing of a thoroughly structured program to make sure that the result of the new system is the anticipated ones. Most system failures are due to inadequate conduct of the implementation phase. This phase is very important because the success of the project depends on it. Having designed the new system in chapter three, it is very important to ascertain the proper operation of the system to ensure that it achieves the aim of the project. The new system has been designed, and every necessary thing has been done to ensure its perfect operation. System implementation is the final stage where the design is put to use. Here we look into various technical aspects that influence the successful implementation of the new system and also determine its effective operation. The activity diagram shows a summary of all the user activities. This all starts with logging into the system. The user enters his or her member id and password. The input is authenticated by the system, and when it's been successfully authenticated, then the privileges are checked. The privileges are checked to ensure that the right main page is shown for each user. This is because the administrator and the employees have different privileges to the application system. For example, a fund member interacts with a system, such as when he/ she logs in successfully is selects a link to view his account statement or contributions. The system displays the particular fund members' statements.

5.2.2 Software Requirements

All modifications made during development are documented in the system implementation document. Also, development tools and source code is provided in the system implementation document for future maintenance. The entire system was developed with a xamp server, text editor (Sublime), MySQL, PHP, Html, JavaScript.

Figure 5.1 order processing

A secure system has the following qualities, and it is required that the new system be tested for them:

Confidentiality: The confidentiality of a secure system is a quality that protects information from unauthorized disclosure, that is, to parties other than the intended recipients.

Integrity: A measure designed to assist the receiver to ensure that the information it receives has not been altered in transit or by anybody other than the source of the information. An intruder should not be able to replace a real message with a fraudulent one.

Authorization and Authentication: Authentication allows the identity of an end-user to be verified. This means that no one may be able to masquerade on the system, posing as the origin or recipient of a message. Authorization is the process of determining whether an end-user has the required permissions or rights to use a service or perform an operation. Access control is an example of authorization.

Availability: Availability involves ensuring that data is protected in such a manner that access to the information is free-flowing and ready when needed.

Non-repudiation: This quality involves ensuring that an occurred action or communication cannot be denied to have been affected by the originating user. This may be done by exchanging authentication information and timestamp.

6.1 Conclusion

This project has been tested and documented, with due consideration being given to flexibility and ease of accessibility. The following includes those things that have been achieved by this project. Adequate security measures have been put in place to ensure correct identification. An interface design that ensures effective categorization of different windows. Three online shopping interfaces for various transactions have been included to demonstrate how a transaction is carried out with UMS E-payment system. Total payment of transaction is reflected on the customer's account to help keep track of payment. A program design that prevents the user from spending the same money twice. The UMS E-payment System concept is a new innovation, and there is still much that could be done to increase its effectiveness. Having considered the concept of the online UMS E-payment system, the following recommendation is hereby suggested. The online or real-time implementation of this project should form the basis for future work, as the present implementation constitutes a stand-alone application program. The implementation of a multi-user version of this project is also recommended. The online transaction interface design implementation in this project makes it a veritable tool for online payment in the supermarket, mini market, merchant shop, etc This shift in client behavior, indicating a shift from traditional to advanced online payment methods, is visible in shopping and banking, as well as with practically all available mobile devices. The statistics are shown in this study signify that the number of customers employing an online mode of payment and making online transactions are continuously growing, hinting at an everlasting acceptance of online payment systems from academia as well as industry. However, the adoption and deployment of several rising technologies carry new opportunities and challenges to the implementation and design of secure online payment systems in the present day as well as in the near future. This study concludes that better integration of online payment systems with the present financial and telecommunication infrastructure is necessary for a propitious future of this payment mode. Furthermore, establishing a common standard for a variety of service providers, improving the compatibility with a large number of customers, overcoming privacy and security concerns, and employing the latest technology could facilitate expeditious adoption of online payment methods and expand the market for such a mode of payment. Future work may be directed towards the legalization of various factors responsible for contributing to the efficacious adoption of online payment systems all over the world

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